

Management Systems and Procedures as Performance Mechanisms for Institutional Growth

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ABSTRACT

Efficient management system is encircled with enormous challenges that require conscious thoughts and carefully assessment of its constituents. Management systems is extensively studied by numerous practitioners and academicians and have established results used by numerous multinational companies as references manuals. This study assessed the management systems and procedures as performance mechanisms for institutional growth. Pieces of literature published on the subject matter was reviewed as supportive mechanisms towards achieving this study's objectives. This study employed descriptive quantitative and correlational methods, which facilitated the gathering, classification and presentation of data that led to constructive discussion and conclusion. This study selected a sample size of 200 employees from two institutions where first-hand information was obtained with the aid of questionnaires. Results shows that, effective employee development facilitate skills development, which enhances exceptional performance. In additional, efficient management systems commitment increases employees motivational level, which leads to outstanding performance and minimises staff turnover. Further facts revealed noted that, compensation play a pivotal role towards organisational development. Results emphasised that, employee recognition for outstanding performance and compensation for innovative contributions instils the culture of exceptional performance, which enhances institutional growth. The relationship between employee development and performance, commitment and performance and compensation and performance disclosed that, when a workforce is well capacitated, engaged and satisfactorily rewarded, the result of such action could be achieving target, which demonstrate competitive excellence. This study is significant to small, medium and largescale organisations. It is also noteworthy to management practitioners and business consultants.

Keywords: *Management Systems, Procedures, Performance Mechanisms, Institutional Growth.*

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INTRODUCTION

Corporate institutions have expressed enormous concerns about their management systems and contribution towards organisational development. However, managing such systems encircled substantial challenges, which stifles the growth and sustainability of such institutions. Therefore, researchers and general management consultants should consider a significant approach to the development of organisations through an efficient performance management system. Though considered strategically significant, institutions acknowledge that, its effects has to be measured from a wider spectrum of operations to ascertain its contribution towards institutional growth. [1,2,3,4,5,6,7] conducted related research on management systems impact on organisations growth, however, they emphasise on financial compensation as the principal element that create performance. Studies disclosed that, performance could only have positive effects on organisations operations if employees are adequately rewarded. Considering previous researches on management systems, which laid emphasis on incentives, this study considerably examine management systems and procedures on organisational development, principally focusing on examining performance planning, employee development, performance appraisal, workforce commitment and compensation management. These constitute management systems with anticipations that, they will create satisfactory outcome and consequently influence growth.

Multinational companies across the world are making efforts to retain their valued employees through various means. One of the prevailing mechanisms that encourage workers achievement is an efficient management system. Handling employee performance is seen as the greatest challenging areas of human resources development practice [8,9,10,9,11,12]. Employees' expectations about performance practices and procedures are interrupted or devastated by the realism of a system that breeds conflicting, problematic and confrontational issues that affect the outcome of results [13,14]. This generate complications for management specialists to establish an efficient management system that eradicates undesirable consequences and produce constructive mechanisms for specific and institutional performance [15,16]. Managers may depend on diversity of procedures, programmes and activities to produce better results. They might

establish critical objectives yet fail to create a system that offers the required support to accomplish those objectives[17,18]. Institutions identify the necessity to create close alignment between goals set at corporate and local levels, which create uncertainty at each category that leads to a degree of discrepancy unpleasant to authorities[19,20]. The process of articulating organizations goals, relating those goals to the performance of people, discloses performance gaps, which prompt actions for solutions, change and evaluation of results. Executives most times expresses that unsatisfactory performance is other peoples fault, not theirs[3,6,21]. However, several research results have established that poor performance could be the cause of ineffective management system, inefficient administration or substandard systems of work [22,23]. Standards provide the basis for both the management of performance and change. Such values are entrenched, linked, continuing, and collectively measured and managed.

Effective management systems is described by authorities who actively pursue policies for continuous improvement and provide the technology, resources and system necessary to meet performance expectations [24,25,26,27,28]. Management processes ensures the achievement of objectives.However, there are concerns that employees could adopt certain behaviours and proceed with specific actions towards achieving organisational goals [29,30].Conceptual performance encompasses job specific elements such as cooperating, dedicating, and enthusiastic exhibition of talents and perseverance, whilst task performance covers certain behaviours different from conceptual presentation[31,15]. Investigation conducted by Bailey et al [25] in 45 organisations focused on a factor influencing performance, which is the opportunity to participate. They emphasised that, consolidating the work process gives non-managerial workers the opportunity to contribute to the effectiveness of a high-performance work-system[16,32,33,34]. Systems theory states that, organizations should be treated as open systems, which changes inputs into outputs. Systems theory is described as input–process– and output–method of handling performance, which measureemployees’contributions to the system[35,36,37]. The knowledge and skills employees bring to a job enable them to perform exceptionally; which prompt human resource management specialists to identify and develop talents for effective service delivery and institutional growth [2,38].Evaluating employees’contribution to organisations performance is not easy; however, evidence on the link between enterprise performance and people management is increasing. Enterprises, which decisively establish opportunities for employees ‘development, expect a return on their investment[39,40,41].Determining development needs is usually a combination of bottom-up and top-down processes.Therefore, executives at all levels should evidently recognise development context and discuss it with team members to ensure that agreed individual needs are consolidated into the team, department, and organisational development plans[38,42,43,44]. Since business consultants are anxious about evaluating the worth of employees, assessing costs in contrast to benefits,prompt the application of suitable motivating tools that enhances outstanding performance[45,46,47]. Preceding description has laid the foundation upon which subsequent segments will thrive. Ensuing elements will review pieces of literature,describe methods of data collection, analyse, discuss results, and compare those results to other works published to create distinct significance of the subject studied.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Planning for Effective Performance

Evaluating enterprise performance have been continually and extensively documented which emphasised the connection between planning and firms' performance. Research results disclosed that efficient planning system improves institutional performance[4,16,17]. Formulating plans for effective performance includeswide-rangingperspectives classified as generating facts, exploring prospects, inspires novel thoughts, increasing incentives and enhances internal communication and collaboration [13,9,18,8]. Developing strategic plans is noteworthy for small,medium and large-scale manufacturing operations. Planning enables an organisation to forecast future advantages and establish precautionary measures to prevent threats[12,15,11]. In their investigation on meta-studies, Santos and Brito [42] established that, there is constructive and substantial connectivity between planning and organisational performance. Planning is the most basic of all managerial functions, which encompasses selection from among alternatives, imminent courses of achievement, which includes departmental goals. Most planning failures arise from managers' inability to truly understand planning and implementation of activities [10,14,26,19,23]. During implementation and control process, plans may require modification to avoid becoming useless or even damaging.Such action implies that, decisions must be made at many stages in the planning process[6,28]. Even though administrative functions are interwoven in practice as a scheme of action, plans are distinctive, as they creates the objectives required for all teams' effort[3,27]. Planning is a significant performance driver that enhances economic and organisational development. However, its thoroughness mirrors in long-term enterprises development[17].

Employee Development

The continued existence of enterprises in competing environments hinge on their capability to develop their workforce to stimulate creativity, establish novelties and invent strategies consistent withefficient management systems[20]. Developing organisations workforce demonstrate a pivotal role in the efficiency of institution management; which improves workers' performance and enhances organisations productivity[24]. For business to accomplish its specified objectives, satisfactory and significant capacity building for personnel should be emphasised[30]. Staff capacity

building is a calculated fortitude to accelerate knowledge of work related competences, abilities, skills and behaviours that are vital for effective job performance and business growth[31]. An enlightened and knowledgeable workforce is considered indispensable to an enterprise sustainable advantage. Training is a powerful instrument, which facilitates the development of competencies for firms' expansion, thus enhancing productivity[29,32]. Most capacity building activities necessitate substantial improvement that is reinforced by adequate financial resources to implement strategic training programmes in multinational companies[34]. Large-scale enterprises could gain additional advantage from personnel with distinct knowledge on the application of learning practices. Large firms may benefit from scale effects in the usage of training practices. This suggests that firm size also have direct influence on training practices[42]. Employees express job satisfaction when their capacities are developed. This lead to increase performance, which propels organisational development. Employee development is a personal and organisational responsibility that requires capacity-building experts to involve all cadres of employees in training programmes[40]. Personnel progression hinge on organisational ethos, approach of top management, and restricted prospects for promotion. If an organization culture support employee development, it will facilitate the increase of performance and encourage active personnel participation in strategic decision-making[37]. Top management also influence employee development since institutional growth is subject to the genuineness of effective high-level administration[46]. Since coaching involves treating employees as partners in achieving departmental and organizational goals, coaching and mentoring plays a significant role towards employee development [47]. By providing coaching, personal and work-related problems can be solved, which increases performance and enhances organisational development [48]. Reviewed pieces of literature described training as a relevant tool in organisational operations. However, the influence of training and its contribution towards organisational growth is not emphasised and such information is considerably significant in all facets of enterprise development. Since the aforementioned components are not emphasised, this study however identified them as a gap, which it determine to address using first-hand information from survey.

Appraisal of Employee Performance

Performance appraisal is a unique and foremost noteworthy human resource management tool used to assess human capital activities, which is intended to encourage workers commitment and enterprise performance. Employee assessment is a prescribed institutional activity carried out in a systematic manner, which provides evaluation between individual performance anticipated and performance provided[49,50,51,52]. Since enterprises can only achieve worthwhile advantage through employees, it is prerogative to evaluate them. PA is conducted yearly or biannually to support administrative decisions such as pay raises and employee development (e.g. identifying training opportunities and areas for improvement)[53,54,55,56]. Performance appraisals provide evidence of supervisors' ability to assess employees appropriately. When a supervisor delivers an inaccurate evaluation of an employee's performance, he loses credibility[57,58]. Positive evaluations are generally found to motivate employees whereas negative evaluations, sometimes improve performance and sometimes deteriorate it. Appraisals are linked to rewards on the basis of performance evaluations which gives employees confidence about their ability to exert their efforts to complement institutions growth[59,60,61,62]. Although it has countless remuneration for corporations, performance appraisal has the equal probability of having a bad impact on enterprises and on employee performance [63,64]. Numerous issues challenging the competence of an effective evaluation system comprises of compensation on engagement, commitment and reliability of workers which stimulates efficiency within an enterprise[65,66,67]. Combining compensation and employee performance leads to commitment on the performance evaluation progression.

Constructive comment on evaluations provide an employee with a sensation of worth, particularly when satisfactory salaries accompanies the process [54]. If a supervisor appraise an employee and delivers unsatisfactory evaluation score as an outcome of the assessment, such act will definitely demotivate the employee from active participation in future assessment endeavours[56]. The substantial role of employee appraisal has become indispensable, therefore, the growth of every enterprise is dependent on how well the performance of employees is efficiently evaluated and achieved[48]. To ascertain workers proficiency about performance systems, it is necessary for enterprises to regulate uninterrupted activities, which help in reassessing their performance thus improving outcomes [52]. Managers can only satisfy employees on a job if such employees are compensated with what they deserve for their performance without attempting to exploit and pay them lower than expected[49]. Firms that encourage employees, provide a platform for innovations, which brings excellent ideas that facilitate firms' viable advantage. Promotion, rise in incentives are exposed to satisfactory performance results; alternatively, a woeful assessment situation produces penalties which serve as a consequence of negative feedback [59]. Such awareness pushes employees to exhibit intelligence to prevent the manifestation of unsatisfactory and unpleasant compensation. If assessment procedure makes the worker feel apprehensive or discourage, this remarkable sensation might disrupt the entire assessment process [60]. Production of evaluation reports should not be delayed and consideration should be shown on time exigencies, as it is part of employees' rights to understand their performance progression[64]. Feedback creates opportunity for better competitive standing and if properly given, there is a likelihood of motivating workers to contribute extensively to the growth and sustainability of organizations[65]. This leads to benefit. However, the absence of feedback generates job unpleasantness amongst

employees; which perceive the structure as ineffectual and discriminating[53]. Prescriptions of performance appraisal reviewed in this section, disclosed the structure of employee evaluation system and certain considerable elements in the appraisal process. Outcomes of staff appraisal and their impact on organisational growth are not discussed in the reviewed literature. In addition, the impact of appraisal results, which recognise outstanding performers for promotion and identify underperformers for further capacity building are also not evident in the review process. As a result, the missing components are classified as fissures, which this study determines to fill in with survey data.

Workforce Commitment

Studies carried out by consultancy agencies established suppositions on factors influencing commitment. Studies disclosed that, successful enterprises are deferential to workers commitment, irrespective of employees' job level[58]. Research conducted in public sector organisations indicated that, fair and equal treatment of employees, impact engagement levels. Staffs that have better intelligence, demonstrate superior probability to reciprocate their expertise at greater stages of institutional engagement[56]. It was also revealed that, the relationship between management practice and commitment is rather indirect. However, further reviewed pieces of literature did not disclose specific model that shows the significant influence of all variables because different employees laid different emphasis on variables influencing commitment[61]. These differences might arise because of discrepancies in job descriptions, gender diversity, and cultural diversification. The difference between engagement and leadership factors i.e., task orientation and relationship orientation considerably overlap[65]. Employee engagement creates a friendly cultural practice that unifies capacities and competences employees bring along to exhibit their aspirations towards achieving strategic organisational objectives[49].

Employee commitment is a broad concept, which requires management commitment and involvement of outstanding performers for fruitful engagement between employers and employees [64]. Concentrating on employee commitment can generate capable and creative workforce. As a result, organizations should design mechanism to improve and cultivate engagement, which necessitates a two-track relationship approach between employing agencies and employees[16]. Engaged employees are conscious about the business environment and such consciousness motivate them to work diligently to increase job performance for organisational development[13]. Staff commitment is a desire of employees' willingness to invest and increase their discretion to support employing agencies succeed in their drive towards a lasting advantage, which goes beyond unpretentious fulfilment with the employment procedure or allegiance to the employer[3]. Most drivers that are found to lead to employee engagement are non-financial in their nature. Therefore, any organization who has committed leadership can achieve the desired level of engagement with less cost of doing it[8]. Employee commitment is the significance of individual characteristics such as talent, abilities, skills, disposition, boldness and personality. It further indicate institutional perspective which includes leadership, physical and social mechanisms and human resources practices that directly influence work performance[6]. The foregoing content demonstrate a broad spectrum of engaging employees in institutional operations. However, the effects such engagements proffer is not evident in the literature. In addition, effective staff commitment, which leads to exceptional performance and organisational development, which is the principal focus of this study, is not seen in the reviewed pieces of literature. Therefore, this study determines to address such gap using first-hand information.

Compensation Management

Researches on compensation management have disclosed constructive outcomes and significances on how rewards influence performance measures. Rewards are classified as significant components, which motivate institutional workforce to unleash their greatest effort to produce innovative philosophies [14]. Reward policy offers explicit guidelines for organizations to establish and manage incentive packages, which reward performance outcomes and support the achievement of business goals[22]. Performance measures that are not affected regularly by rewards inspire practitioners to re-examine certain concepts and practices. Rewards should be utilised judiciously by systematically considering its comparative importance to employee performance[31]. Total reward is the combination of all types of intrinsic and extrinsic rewards (financial and non-financial) made available to employees for institutional growth[24]. Rewards and their influence are becoming issues of concern an efficient management system. Therefore, organisations should formulate principles that describe procedures, rules and strategies for effective compensation management [28]. The principal objective of reward management is to reward employees fairly, justly and reliably in relation to their worth in the organization. Reward is one of the various organizational elements used to enhance employees and organizational performance[38]. Compensation does not only concerned with pay and employee benefits; it also encompasses non-financial which includes recognising employees contribution, capacitating and increasing employees competences to improve task accountability[37]. Much of the published works on this subject has shown countless elements of disagreement on whether reward systems (extrinsic, intrinsic and social rewards) could increase employees' performance [35]. Organizations can gain more performance benefits from their diligent employees; if rewards are properly aligned to organisations strategies and performance outcomes [68]. Even though the foregoing reviewed pieces of literature describe compensation comprehensively, however, compensation as a strategic motivating element towards employee performance is not emphasised and the influence of financial and nonfinancial rewards towards employee performance

and organisational development is also not evident in the literature. Therefore, this study decides to fill in gaps identified in the review process, with the aid of survey data.

METHODS

Research Design

Effective data collection requires a suitable research design, which outline various steps necessary for successful compilation, analysis and description of data. Any research that focuses on the collection of primary data to obtain first-hand information should establish a constructive research design to ease the process. Research design outlines the processes necessary for collection, measurement, and analysis of information which helps the researcher to structure/or solve business problems. Once the researcher has identified and established the broad approach to the research problem, the next step is to prepare an outline or proposal of the study, which specifies the procedures necessary for achieving stated objectives in a robust manner. Quantitative research creates data through the practice of large-scale investigation, using techniques such as questionnaires or organised interviews. This study adopted descriptive quantitative survey and correlational method which includes gathering, classification and presentation of data that prompted thorough analysis and discussions of contents studied. The aforementioned method was deemed suitable for the assessment of performance elements and their contributions towards institutional growth.

Sampling Technique

This study was conducted in Freetown, focusing on assessing management systems within two financial institutions to ascertain the influence of management systems and procedures on institutions development. Selecting appropriate sampling techniques depends on one's research questions and objectives. Afterwards, one's desire to have close contact with respondents in a certain area where his/her sampling frame is may influence his/her choice of probability sampling technique. Sample should be selected from an entire population since it is impracticable for one to collect data from a whole population. Depending on the circumstance or case studies used, one might be able to collect data from two or three organisations [65]. Some research questions made it theoretically practical for the collection of data from an entire population; however, that could be prevented with the cost involved in the process [1]. More time can be spent in designing and piloting data collection for small samples, which shows high level of accuracy than larger samples. Collecting data from a small sample is more detailed and interviewers engaged in such process can exhibit high quality and efficiency in the process of obtaining data. Each case selected from a population using probability sampling is known and there is a likelihood that all cases within such frame equally have the chance of been understood clearly. This shows that, there is a possibility to respond to research questions accurately to achieve the objectives required to strategically estimate the characteristics of the population from the sample drawn. Simple random sampling also referred to as random sampling requires the selection of samples at random from sampling frames with the aid of a computer or random number table. When a sampling frame has been chosen and requires a representative sample size to be selected, further steps necessitates the selection of the most suitable sampling technique to obtain a representative sample. This investigation employed probability sampling and adopted simple random sampling procedures, which facilitated the selection of sample units from the sample frame; such processes are deemed more suitable for this endeavour.

Population and Sample Size

The size of sample needed and structure of sampling frame and sampling technique may influence one's decision in a research process. The larger the sample size, the lower the likelihood of experiencing error in generalising the population. The sample size selected is governed by the level of assurance that the characteristics of data collected, represents the total population. The required accuracy made from selected sample, types of analysis undertaken, that is; categories in which data are subdivided shows minimum threshold for numerous statistical techniques for each cell and the population from which representative samples are drawn. Nevertheless, it is worth remarking that, unbiased larger sample size serves as credible representative sample of a population from which they are drawn than smaller samples and the mean calculated for such sample is more likely equal to the mean for the population [65]. This study used a sample size of 200 employees from two financial institutions. The selection process of sample units range from nonsupervisory to managerial employees and sample selected serves as satisfactory representative sample for this study.

Data Collection Instrument and Procedure

When questionnaires are designed to obtain primary information, preliminary acquaintance must first be done to establish familiarity with interviewees or participants [44]. Pre-notification on data collection was done by sending letters to institutions imploring them to grant permission in order to prevent rejection or ineffective participation in the research process. Questionnaires are relatively easy to use, inexpensive, and are often the more reasonable substitute for quantifying unobservable paradigms such as attitudes, values and preferences, intentions, and personalities (Fletcher 2001). Questionnaires and interviews are usually conducted for the purpose of asking questions to ascertain people's thoughts about, and feelings towards, issues, events, behaviours, and so on. This study obtained first-hand information with the aid of questionnaires. 250 questionnaires were circulated to respondents, however, 200 were retrieved which

classify sample units as follows: 120 men (60%) and 80 women (40%). We adopted the Linkert scale system, which shows the following description: 5=Strongly Agree, 4=Agree, 3=Neutral, 2=Disagree, 1=Strongly Disagree.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics on the distribution of respondents profile and employee development

	N	Range	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std.		Skewness	Kurtosis			
						Std. Error	Deviation		Std. Error	Statistic		
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic		
Gender	200	1	1	2	1.40	.035	.491	.241	.411	.172	-1.849	.342
Age	200	3	1	4	2.50	.073	1.027	1.055	.000	.172	-1.127	.342
Designation	200	3	1	4	2.65	.079	1.111	1.234	-.162	.172	-1.326	.342
BODCS	200	1	1	2	1.60	.035	.491	.241	-.411	.172	-1.849	.342
PIEP	200	2	1	3	2.25	.054	.768	.590	-.461	.172	-1.168	.342
TIEP	200	2	1	3	2.35	.051	.728	.530	-.649	.172	-.861	.342
CISEST	200	1	1	2	1.55	.035	.499	.249	-.203	.172	-1.979	.342
TEPEP	200	2	1	3	2.25	.054	.768	.590	-.461	.172	-1.168	.342
PEELCT	200	2	1	3	2.30	.051	.716	.513	-.515	.172	-.918	.342
PRPETF	200	2	1	3	2.25	.054	.768	.590	-.461	.172	-1.168	.342
TIOK	200	2	1	3	2.30	.051	.716	.513	-.515	.172	-.918	.342
PEETE	200	2	1	3	2.35	.051	.728	.530	-.649	.172	-.861	.342
CEPTD	200	1	1	2	1.55	.035	.499	.249	-.203	.172	-1.979	.342
Valid N (listwise)	200											

Employee development is a strategic component in organisational development, which increases employees' skills and competencies for exceptional job performance. However, financial institutions have expressed several concerns about the huge cost involve in conducting strategic training and such challenges have led to drawbacks in the competitive landscape. The conduct of this investigation considerably include gender, age and designations of respondents. This study used a sample unit of 200 respondents from two financial institutions, which are classified as 120 male and 80 female. The age classification range as follows: 18-25, 26-35, 36-45 and 46+. Designations of respondents are categorised as Technical/clerical, Supervisor, Manager and Professionals. Reviewed pieces of literature describe the comprehensive significance of employee development; however, there are no indications about the contributions of training and development towards increasing employee performance and organisational development. In the analysis conducted on data obtained from survey, respondents noted that, staff development is a considerable organisational development strategy, which increases employees' motivation and performance level. Regarding planning for the conduct of training programmes, respondents indicated that, training programmes are well planned and effectively implemented. Increase in employees skills and competencies is most times determined by effective and efficient training programmes conducted by organisations. Survey results shows that, strategic training programmes conducted by the institutions develop employees skills and competencies for effective job performance. Outstanding performance is the principal focus of every organisations workforce, since achieving target set, helps to retain high-class performers. However, respondents registered their opinions that, efficient management systems enhances exceptional performance. This increases employees' efficiency level. Authorities in institutions usually identify performance fissures in the implementation of strategic activities, which specialists note that such problems are caused by of lack of effective staff capacity building. However, respondents established that, employee development programmes organised by the institutions reduces performance fissures and knowledge employees gain in training is transferred to their daily routine work, which improves organisational performance. Competitive advantage has been the thrust of many corporate institutions since gaining such advantage classify organisations at strategic level in the competitive landscape. In relation to aforesaid, respondents indicated that, an efficient management system facilitate employees empowerment for competitive excellence and enhances professionalism and employee career development. Results obtained in this segment has comparative significance to studies conducted by Abbas and Yaqoob [59], Cosh and Weeks [54], Hill and Stewart [57] & Kennedy et al [52] in their investigations about the role of training on employee performance. However, this study demonstrate distinct contributions about the impact efficient management system have on employee performance and organisational development.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics on the distribution of respondents on workforce commitment

N	Range	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std.		Skewness	Kurtosis
					Deviation	Variance		

	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error
COAS	200	2	1	3	2.15	.056	.794	.631	-.275	.172	-1.363	.342
SEDAP	200	2	1	3	2.25	.054	.768	.590	-.461	.172	-1.168	.342
SOJET	200	2	1	3	2.20	.053	.750	.563	-.346	.172	-1.152	.342
CEESE	200	2	1	3	2.30	.051	.716	.513	-.515	.172	-.918	.342
PISWMD	200	2	1	3	2.25	.054	.768	.590	-.461	.172	-1.168	.342
SEIPE	200	2	1	3	2.30	.051	.716	.513	-.515	.172	-.918	.342
EMEE	200	2	1	3	2.25	.054	.768	.590	-.461	.172	-1.168	.342
DEEPD	200	2	1	3	2.30	.051	.716	.513	-.515	.172	-.918	.342
SEEPE	200	2	1	3	2.30	.051	.716	.513	-.515	.172	-.918	.342
MEEHS	200	2	1	3	2.25	.054	.768	.590	-.461	.172	-1.168	.342
Valid N (listwise)	200											

Modern enterprise operations requires effective employee commitment that cultivate the notion of exceptional performance. Achieving and exceeding targets emanates from a diligent workforce, whose competencies is facilitated by effective engagement. For competitive advantage to be achieved and maintained, unceasing staff commitment is required. Reviewed pieces of literature did not establish specific elements that constitute effective employee commitment; however, survey data disclosed relevant issues surrounding employee commitment which note that, the various institutions offers career advancement opportunity to all categories of staff as engagement strategy. Regarding skills development, respondents indicated that, institutions provide adequate support for employee skills development to enhance exceptional performance. Effective job performance requires adequate tools to empower institutions workforce towards addressing performance challenges. In this regard, respondents emphatically stated that, tools for effective job performance are evident in all sectors of the institutions. Respondents disclosed that, because of the institutions constant engagement with employees, it cultivate a system of self-improvement, which give staffs confidence to perform their duties efficiently. Employee wellbeing is a great concern towards job satisfaction and retention; however, turnover or attrition is normally triggered by the negligence of staff welfare, which disrupt the smooth flow of organisations operations. In this regard, respondents established that, management demonstrate profound interest in staff wellbeing, which give employees confidence to remain in the institutions. Thorough data analysis disclosed that, effective and efficient staff engagement enhances employee motivation, which further increase performance and productivity. Constant staff engagement identifies deficiencies, which respondents note that, commitment decreases performance deficiencies and address critical challenges encircling the achievement of strategic objectives. Respondents further noted that, effective staff engagement leads to outstanding performance and minimises employee turnover. Results achieved in this study about workforce commitment is supported by studies conducted by Mone and London [5], Bailey et al [25] & Gupta and Upadhyay [1] in their quest to discover factors influencing performance with specific emphasis on engagement. However, distinction between this study and previous research on employee commitment is that, previous studies focus on specific drivers of engagement whilst this study categorically examined engagement from a wider spectrum of organisational development. In this regard, this study has been able to establish employee commitment's influence on performance and organisational development.

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics on the distribution of respondents on compensation management

	N	Range	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Variance	Skewness	Kurtosis
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic
TOOCES	200	2	1	3	2.20	.053	.750	.563	-.346
SAJCGPS	200	1	1	2	1.55	.035	.499	.249	-.203
RABEAP	200	2	1	3	2.25	.054	.768	.590	-.461
SWPER	200	2	1	3	2.30	.051	.716	.513	-.515
REICOT	200	2	1	3	2.20	.053	.750	.563	-.346
REPTE	200	2	1	3	2.30	.051	.716	.513	-.515
REAIMEF	200	2	1	3	2.25	.054	.768	.590	-.461
POCEBC	200	2	1	3	2.30	.051	.716	.513	-.515
AEPIF	200	2	1	3	2.30	.051	.716	.513	-.515

CESIC	200	1	1	2	1.60	.035	.491	.241	-.411	.172	-1.849	.342
Valid N (listwise)	200											

Compensation plays an essential role in influencing employees' performance for competitive excellence. Numerous schools of thought and management practitioners have established uncountable reasons that influence performance with specific emphasis on compensation. Equitable distribution of rewards necessitate exceptional performance and serve as contributing factor towards retaining high-class performers. Facts derived from reviewed literature noted that rewards play a contributing role towards triggering performance. However, specifications such as financial and nonfinancial rewards are not dealt with separately and emphasis on their contributions are not made evident from facts derived from the review process. Nevertheless, facts obtained from analysis drawn from survey data established that, institutions operate efficient compensation systems, which allocate rewards according to job grades. Respondents indicated that, additional allocations are made based on employees' exceptional performance, which exceeds performance target. Regarding employee recognition for innovative contributions, respondents emphatically stated that, employees are recognised and rewarded for satisfactory work performance and innovative contributions towards organisational development. Performance targets are set in every spheres of organisational operations to ensure the attainment of standards. Analysis of data obtained from survey shows that, employees at the various institutions are recognised for exceeding targets. In addition, respondents also indicated that, annual recognition events held by the institutions increases employees' motivation level. Respondents further registered that, employees are offered comprehensive benefit package, which probably influence their commitment towards achieving strategic objectives. Regarding the role incentives play towards influencing exceptional performance, respondents specified that, financial inducement accelerate outstanding performance. However, further indications shows that, compensation influences competitive excellence and sustainability. Facts derived from survey data regarding rewards is supported by results obtained from studies conducted by Risher [6], Jane [68] & Armstrong and Stephens [18] in their determination to establish the role incentives play towards employee performance. Interestingly, results of this survey made distinct contributions that is not evident in previous studies.

Table 4: Descriptive Statistics on the distribution of respondents on performance appraisal

	N	Range	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std.	Deviation	Variance	Skewness	Kurtosis	Std.	Std.
					Statistic	Error	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Error	Statistic	Error
					Statistic							
MESPOT	200	2	1	3	2.20	.053	.750	.563	-.346	.172	-1.152	.342
CIOUSA	200	1	1	2	1.55	.035	.499	.249	-.203	.172	-1.979	.342
CEAPI	200	2	1	3	2.30	.051	.716	.513	-.515	.172	-.918	.342
CEEELAP	200	1	1	2	1.55	.035	.499	.249	-.203	.172	-1.979	.342
PCBPAP	200	1	1	2	1.55	.035	.499	.249	-.203	.172	-1.979	.342
CAPEP	200	2	1	3	2.25	.054	.768	.590	-.461	.172	-1.168	.342
SEFDOP	200	2	1	3	2.30	.051	.716	.513	-.515	.172	-.918	.342
CAPFS	200	2	1	3	2.25	.054	.768	.590	-.461	.172	-1.168	.342
BORDP	200	2	1	3	2.30	.051	.716	.513	-.515	.172	-.918	.342
PRAEMD	200	1	1	2	1.55	.035	.499	.249	-.203	.172	-1.979	.342
Valid N (listwise)	200											

Assessing employees performance level is determine by a structured staff appraisal mechanism, which identifies employees' efficiency level. Promotions and recommendations for further capacity building emanates from results obtained from an efficient employee appraisal system. In this regard, the conduct of such process should be free from resentment and biasness as it jeopardises the credibility and trust of institutions performance appraisal system. Pieces of literature reviewed in support of institutions appraisal system did not disclose effects of staff appraisal on organisations development. However, survey information indicates that, institutions have efficient management systems that identifies outstanding and underperformers, which facilitate further capacity building to strengthen low-class performers. Respondents disclosed that, institutions constant engagement on employee counselling, improves performance appraisal results. Further indications disclosed that, staff appraisal discloses employee efficiency level, which determines performance outcomes. Respondents noted that, the conduct of staff capacity building emanates from results obtained in appraisal process, which indicates deficiencies that triggered further actions for staff development. Respondents established that, performance challenges identified in the appraisal process are acted upon and addressed promptly to prevent an extension of such unpleasant process. Regarding the evidence of standards in the various sectors of the institutions, respondents firmly supported that standards are evident in all departments. Consultations on the conduct of

an efficient staff appraisal is relevant for ease of the process. However, respondents registered that, performance appraisal consultations are fruitful and sustainable, which improves results obtained in evaluations. Descriptive analysis of survey data disclosed that, performance rating are done based on outcomes, therefore, results obtained in evaluations helps management to make strategic decisions. This result is supported by numerous studies conducted by Boselie and Boon [26], Brown et al. [62], DeNisi and Pritchard [29], Fletcher [24] & Giangreco et al [65] in their investigations on employee appraisal. Nevertheless, previous studies laid emphasis on theoretical significance whilst this study emphasises on practical significance of the subject matter, which exhibit significant contributions of this study to organisational development.

Table 5: Correlations between employee development and performance, compensation and performance and commitment and performance

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
SEMOPT	1.000									
MPIEL	.883	1.000								
TEOPE	.959	.921	1.000							
TIOPK	.917	.954	.959	1.000						
SEIPE	.917	.954	.959	1.000	1.000					
DPDEE	.917	.954	.959	1.000	1.000	1.000				
SEEPE	.917	.954	.959	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000			
SWERP	.917	.954	.959	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000		
REPTE	.917	.954	.959	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	
PEALF	.917	.954	.959	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000

This study established constructive and positive correlations between compensation and performance, employee development and performance and commitment and performance. It is evident that, a well capacitated workforce with the required skills and competencies exhibit outstanding performance, which leads to organisational development. It is further noted that, an efficient training and development programme determines performance improvement, which strengthens organisations human capital for competitive excellence. However, strategic employee engagement facilitate commitment and prevent turnover. Efficient management system instils a culture of high-class performance, which position institutions strategically in the competitive landscape. The relationship between compensation and performance demonstrate a unique segment of exceptional performance. Incentives are classified as the most influential elements that triggers performance. Implementation and equitable distribution of financial and nonfinancial rewards, influences employee retention. Comparative significance between employee development and performance demonstrate that, performance improvement is orchestrated by employees increased skills and competencies. In addition, effective engagement influences staff commitment, which leads to organisations citizenship. The connection between employee development, employee commitment and compensation, facilitate exceptional performance, which enhances institutional growth.

CONCLUSION

Investigating management systems from a wider spectrum of organisational development encompasses many considerable elements that requires critical assessment for competitive advantage. Efficient management system plays a significant role towards effective and efficient management of institutions operations. However, numerous practitioners underscored that, sustainable enterprises are those that have efficient management systems. Such facts is substantiated by quantum of publications on performance management. This study however, assessed management systems and procedures as performance mechanisms for institutional. In this regard, considerable pieces of literature was reviewed which established significant contributions made by numerous researchers. This study employed descriptive quantitative and correlational methods, which facilitated the gathering, classification and presentation of data that enabled descriptive analysis and constructive discussion on the subject studied. Primary data obtained in this study was facilitated by questionnaires distributed to institutions, which revealed significant issues about the subject matter. Retrieved survey information established that, employee development enhances employees' skills and competencies for effective job performance. Further highlights stated that, employee commitment increases staff motivational level towards exceeding performance targets. Considerable facts established about incentives indicated that, judicious use of financial and nonfinancial rewards stimulate employees extrinsic towards achieving exceptional performance. The relationship between employee development and performance, commitment and performance and compensation and performance established that, such elements constitute the growth and sustainability of institutions. This study is noteworthy to strategic management practitioners, human capital development specialists and general management consultants as it serves as reference manual towards institutional growth. However, further examination on the subject matter could be

done through an assessment of individual components, expansion of sample frame and or sample size or perhaps employ different methods of data collection or analysis.

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